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ON THE APPARENT ABSENCE OF *MACHAON*-COMPLEX
TAXA (*Lepidoptera Papilionidae*) ON THE ISLAND OF LINOSA
(PELAGIAN ISLAND GROUP)

SUMMARY

The volcanic of Linosa, which lies on the southern flank of the Pantelleria Rift, was never physically connected to any other landmass within the central Mediterranean area. Its uninterrupted isolation makes it an interesting subject for research in island biogeography. After the endemic taxon *aferpilaggi* from the island of Lampedusa was confirmed under *Papilio sabarae*, the discovery necessitated a field mission to Linosa to investigate the status of any *machaon*-complex taxa on the island. Such investigation was deemed especially relevant since *Papilio machaon* is known to occur on the Maltese islands, which lie on the northern shoulder of the graben, east-north-east of Linosa. Thorough field investigations were conducted during a four-day field visit. All phases of metamorphosis were searched for throughout the entire island, paying special attention to areas where larval host-plants were present. Informal interviews were also conducted with specific stakeholders. Weather conditions were optimal during the visit, yet there was no trace of any *machaon*-complex taxon on the island of Linosa. Such absence was also confirmed by interviewees.

Keywords: dispersal, geographical isolation, Mediterranean biogeography, *Papilio machaon*, *Papilio sabarae*.

RIASSUNTO

L'isola vulcanica di Linosa, che è situata sul fianco meridionale del Rift di Pantelleria, non è stata mai collegata fisicamente ad altre masse terrestri dell'area Mediterranea. Il suo isolamento ininterrotto la rende un interessante soggetto per ricerche di biogeografia insulare. A seguito della conferma del taxon endemico *Papilio sabarae aferpilaggi* nell'isola di Lampedusa, si è resa necessaria una missione in campo a Linosa per investigare lo status di eventuali taxa del gruppo *machaon* in quest'isola. Questa ricerca è stata considerata molto rilevante in quanto *Papilio machaon* è noto per le isole Maltesi, che si trovano nel fianco settentrionale della fossa tettonica, a est-nordest di Linosa. Sono state condotte a Linosa approfondite ricerche durante una visita di campo di quattro giorni,

sono state cercate molto accuratamente tutte le fasi della metamorfosi del *Papilio* in tutta l'isola, facendo particolare attenzione alle aree in cui erano presenti le piante nutrici delle forme larvali. Inoltre sono state condotte interviste informali con alcune persone. Le condizioni climatiche sono state ottime durante la visita, ma non è stata trovata traccia di alcuna specie appartenente al complesso *machaon* a Linosa. Questa assenza è stata confermata anche dalle persone intervistate.

Parole chiave: dispersione, isolamento geografico, biogeografia Mediterranea, *Papilio machaon*, *Papilio saharae*.

INTRODUCTION

Papilio machaon Linnaeus, 1758 is an iconic species of the Family Papilionidae, with a range that extends across two biogeographical realms. Its associated taxa from the Mediterranean region, namely its various subspecies and closely related species, including *Papilio saharae* Oberthür, 1879, and *Papilio hospiton* Géne, 1839, have over the years received considerable attention from varying points of view, including biogeographical, morphometric and molecular (OBERTHÜR, 1879; CLARKE & SHEPPARD, 1956; SEYER, 1986; CLARKE & LARSEN, 1986; MARINI & TRENTINI, 1989; PITTAWAY *et al.*, 1994; SPERLING & HARRISON, 1994; PELLECCIA *et al.*, 2002; TARRIER & DELACRE, 2008; TSHIKOLOVETS, 2011; CASSAR, 2018; 2023; DUPUIS & SPERLING, 2020; DOMAGALA & LIS, 2022; NAZARI *et al.*, 2023). Some studies also focused on or delved into the possibility of contact zones and natural hybridisation (STROBINO, 1970; PIERRON, 1990; TENNENT, 1996; BENYAMINI, 2017; TODISCO *et al.*, 2023), while very recently, it was established that a new subspecies of *P. saharae* occurred on the island of Lampedusa, which was subsequently described (CASSAR & CATANIA, 2022; CASSAR *et al.*, 2023). Notwithstanding the fact that Lampedusa forms part of Italian and therefore European political jurisdiction, the island lies south of the Pantelleria-Linosa graben system, on its north African flank (CIVILE *et al.*, 2010; SPATOLA *et al.*, 2018).

The islands of Lampedusa, Lampione (some 16 km to its west) and Linosa (some 42 kilometres to its north) form part of the Pelagian island group. While the calcareous Lampedusa was physically connected to the North African mainland during the Pleistocene, the origins of Linosa are volcanic. As a consequence, Linosa has never formed part of a larger continental landmass during its geologically recent subaerial existence since the mid-Pleistocene (ROSSI *et al.*, 1996); its submarine origins commenced around 1 million years ago (AGNESI & FEDERICO, 1995). It is typical of a scoria cone formation, the topography of which is characterised by pyroclastic hills produced by monogenetic volcanism as a result of hydrovolcanic eruptions during at least three main episodes, between >1 and >0.5 Ma (GRASSO *et al.*,

1985; LANTI *et al.*, 1988; PECCERILLO, 2005; ROMAGNOLI *et al.*, 2020); currently, its subaerial altitude is that of 195 m a.s.l.

As in the case of other volcanic islands, the flora of Linosa, mostly xerophilous resulting from primary succession processes, would have slowly established itself passively via various mechanisms of dispersal, including the agency of avifauna, anthropogenic activity (inclusive of commerce and trade), and potentially, wave and wind dynamics. Apart from the various agriculture-related species and cultivars, and the shrubbery introduced for embellishment purposes over the years of human colonisation of the island, the natural vegetation that established itself over time would have been able to adapt to a semi-arid environment [Köppen climate type: BSh: Hot semi-arid (steppe) climate (KOTTEK *et al.*, 2006)] and exposure to winds, maritime aerosols and other natural weather-related phenomena, as well as to loose and rapidly draining volcanic soils.

Some of the plant assemblages present include elements of the Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-desert scrub (92/43 EU ‘Habitats’ Directive code: 5330), which occupies the most extensive cover. These include the *Crithmo-Limonietalia* characterised by endemic *Limonium* spp., on the sea cliffs (code: 1240); pseudo-steppe with grasses and annuals of the *Thero-Brachypodietea* (Annex I Priority habitat type, code: 6220); and low *Euphorbia* formations (code: 5320), an assemblage that is considered a transition between rupestral vegetation and cliff-top phryganas. Other assemblages that are represented, albeit within small, limited areas, include annual vegetation of drift lines, notably *Cakiletea maritimae* (code: 1210), endemic phryganas of the *Euphorbio-Verbascion* (code: 5430), chasmophytic vegetation on rocky outcrops and slopes (code: 8220), and a remnant arborescent matorral with *Juniperus* spp., (code: 5210), quite restricted spatially on the island (BRULLO & SIRACUSA, 1996; LEGAMBIENTE, 2009; PASTA *et al.*, 2017; Natura 2000 Standard Data Form (SIC ITA040001) – version 19.4.17–2019).

During its relatively short subaerial existence, geologically speaking, Linosa would have been subject to climatic episodes operating globally as well as regionally within the central Mediterranean area. Two such phenomena that would have created conditions suitable for the dispersal of immigrant invertebrate biota (among other taxa) within the region. The first are the interstadials, when short-term phases of milder climate punctuated glacial periods during the Pleistocene. The interglacials would also have created appropriate conditions; however, eustatic sea levels rose at this time, as a result of which low-lying terrestrial land-bridges, stepping stone islands and promontories would have become submerged (NEBOUT & GRAZZINI, 1991; HUNT, 1997; HUGHES *et al.*, 2006; CASSAR *et al.*, 2008). The other important phenomenon, often overlooked, is the occurrence of cyclical North African

Humid Periods (NAHP), which provided a window of opportunity for dispersal across northwest Africa during the NAHPs' *circa* 21,000-year cycles, when the Sahara Desert experienced increased levels of precipitation (ARMSTRONG *et al.*, 2023).

Naturally, as climatic conditions changed over geological time, species that would have successfully established populations in vacant niches on Linosa during episodes of immigrant dispersal either adapted or disappeared, as species turnover (resulting from the balance between colonisation and extinction processes) and ensuing environmental conditions subsequently shaped the biotic make-up of the island.

Even if no previous records of *machaon*-complex taxa appear to exist for Linosa (VODĂ *et al.*, 2016; ROMANO, 2020), notwithstanding the presence of suitable larval host-plants (e.g. *Ruta chalepensis* and *Foeniculum vulgare* ssp. *piperitum*) on the island (LAGHETTI *et al.*, 1996; authors' pers. obs. June 2023), the volcanic island tends to lie relatively close, geographically, to both Lampedusa and the Maltese islands where such taxa occur. Following the discovery of a new subspecies *Papilio sabarae aferpillaggi* Cassar, Catania & Cotton, 2023 on Lampedusa, the next reasonable step was to investigate the presence of this or any other related taxon on Linosa through a dedicated survey.

AIMS

The primary objective of the field visit to Lampedusa and Linosa, which took place during the initial two weeks of June 2023, and of which four days (06–09 June) were dedicated to fieldwork on Linosa, was to search for two target species, namely, (i) *Myrmecophilus baronii* Baccetti, 1966 and (ii) for any stage of metamorphosis belonging to the *machaon*-complex. The present contribution focuses on the latter.

METHODS

During the four-day field visit, the entire island was surveyed by car (to ensure that the island's full extent was adequately assessed), on foot (to conduct walkover searches in areas adjacent to existing roads and treks, as well as within locations difficult to access by vehicle), and by UAV – unmanned aerial vehicle (to examine biotopes on inaccessible topography and similarly risky terrain in search of suitable host plant habitats – Fig. 1). The drone used during this survey was a DJI Mini 3 Pro with zoom capability, featuring

Fig. 1 — Drone imagery showing search sequence (L to R) during host-plant habitat searches on craggy topography, including steep slopes and rugged terrain.

4K/60fps HDR and MP4 video format (image sensor: 1/1.3-inch CMOS, 48 MP; transmission range: 12 km FCC).

Moreover, informal interviews were conducted with twelve individuals, comprising local people and visiting naturalists. The former group included people with cultivated land and/or private gardens, while the latter subset consisted of ornithologists, including bird-ringers, who were regular visitors to the island, engaged in a programme concerned with the eradication of rats from around seabird populations.

The research mission was authorised by the *Assessorato Regionale dell'Agricoltura, dello Sviluppo rurale e della Pesca mediterranea (Dipartimento Regionale dello Sviluppo Rurale e Territoriale) – Servizio 2° – Riserve Naturali, Aree Protette e Turismo Ambientale*. Prot. n° 21904, 15 Mar. 2023.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Although not as widespread or abundant as on the island of Lampedusa, both *Ruta chalepensis* and *Foeniculum vulgare* ssp. *piperitum* (the predominant larval host-plants in the region) are present on Linosa. The former occurs on exposed rocky terrain, often within garrigue and phrygana mosaics, while the latter generally colonises roadsides where an element of disturbance is evident. Concentrations of both these plant species were noted to occur in the area of Monte Vulcano. At the time of survey, *R. chalepensis* was observed on the Monte Vulcano cone's slopes from road level to higher elevations in scattered patches, while *F. vulgare* ssp. *piperitum* was present within areas closer to the road and on some of the uncultivated parcels of land that bisect the landscape between Monte Vulcano and Monte Rosso, extending eastward into the natural valley that stretches towards the main town's northern regions. In other localities across the island, where larval host-plants were

encountered, coverage was noticeably sparser. In the vast majority of cases, both *R. chalepensis* and *F. vulgare* ssp. *piperitum* were observed to be in a healthy state of growth, with many plants in bloom; some of the more exposed shrubs of *R. chalepensis* were already developing green seed pods at the time of survey.

Adult butterflies were primarily sought in diverse locations, ranging from sea level to accessible hilltops. Observation periods took place from early morning, throughout peak hours as temperatures became gradually warmer, and extended to late afternoon. Given that *machaon*-complex taxa are largely known to frequent annual swards and garrigue environments as well as fallow fields and grasslands, especially where nectar-rich flowering plants and larval host plants occur, wide-ranging searches for adult butterflies, ova, larvae, and pupae were carried out systematically across such habitats throughout the island. Special attention was given to hill-topping behaviour, where males would patrol relatively large tracts ranging from lower slopes to the summits of hills as they engage in mate-locating behaviour to seek newly emerged females. Hill-topping is essential, as females may otherwise need to cover considerable distances to find a mate, especially if local populations are small and sparse (SCOTT, 1968). Particular attention was also given to private gardens across the island, especially within the main town, where large *Lantana camara* bushes (known to be very attractive to butterflies as a nectaring source) were in full bloom. Notwithstanding the highly favourable field conditions and the significant investment in both time and effort, no adult *machaon*-complex butterflies were encountered.

Wherever larval host-plants were located during walkover surveys or via the use of the drone, a systematic examination of individual plants was conducted, searching for ova and larvae from the top fresh buds and leaves to the lower sections of each shrub. Typically, ova of *machaon*-complex taxa are deposited beneath fresh leaves, within closed sepals, and on petals. Whenever ova are deposited on flower buds, the larvae in stages L1, L2, and L3 initially feed on the flowers. As they grow and develop, larvae would tend to move downward along the plant stems to seek shelter from predators during the day. Despite these thorough searches, no ova or larvae were found during field investigations.

The search for pupae, which are usually found attached to ashlar and rubble walls or to the stems of the food plant itself, was carried out in close proximity of larval host-plants. Particular attention was focused on locating pupae, especially those of the darker form, on the predominantly charcoal grey/black volcanic rocks prevalent on Linosa. Pupal polymorphism appears to be an adaptation to the colour of the surrounding environment at the

pupation site, with colouration being determined in the mature larva shortly before pupation, even though its significance is not fully understood. Notwithstanding, pupal colour polymorphism appears to be intricately linked in-part to seasonal timing (WIKLUND, 1975; *pers. obs.* AC). Colour variation to match the surroundings may serve as a defence mechanism against predators such as birds, micro-mammals, and lizards. As in the case of the adults and earlier developmental stages of metamorphosis, no pupae or empty pupal cases were detected during dedicated searches.

Informal interviews with island residents and visiting naturalists (during which, photographs of the adult and the larva of *Papilio machaon* were shown to those interviewees who appeared unfamiliar with the species) established that none of the candidates had ever seen anything remotely similar. Some interviewees ventured to describe other species of butterflies they associated with particular times of the year that coincided with multigenerational butterfly passage, referring specifically to *Vanessa cardui* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Colias croceus* (Geoffroy, 1785) and other Pierid butterflies (referred to generically as “whites”), and *Danaus chrysippus* (Linnaeus, 1758). The field knowledge of many of those interviewed demonstrated that they were in a position to capably identify one butterfly species from another; this observation further reinforced the notion that a *machaon*-complex taxon does not occur on the island.

It is surmised that the island’s uninterrupted isolation, coupled by its respective distance from North Africa, Lampedusa, Malta, and Sicily, where *machaon*-complex taxa are present, may have served as a physical barrier that prevented any such taxa from establishing a presence on the volcanic island of Linosa. This is not surprising, given that field experimentation involving telemetry on *P. machaon* in recent years has demonstrated the species’ reluctance to undertake sea crossings of even exceedingly short distances (GRECH *et al.*, 2024). The apparent absence of any *machaon*-complex taxa on Linosa demonstrates a clear divide, at least for the islands in the central Mediterranean area, between *P. saharae* and *P. machaon* groups, where the former, *P. s. aferpilaggi*, occurs on Lampedusa, and the latter, *P. machaon*, on Malta and Sicily (Fig. 2).

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Fig. 2 — Lampedusa (geographic range of endemic subspecies *Papilio sabarae aferpilaggi* Cassar, Catania, Cotton, 2023) and Linosa lying on the southern shoulder of the Pantelleria Rift, and the Maltese islands (where *Papilio machaon melitensis* Eller, 1936, often considered a synonym of ssp. *sphyrus* Hübner, [1823], occurs) lies on the northern flank, among other tracts of land, within the central Mediterranean area. The Sicily Channel graben system is clearly visible.

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